

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXVIII. Complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with NOON and ONOONO donor azodye ligands

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Complexes of divalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg have been prepared with azodye ligands, bis[3,3'-di(*p*-nitrophenylazo)]-2,2'-dihydroxydinaphthalene (LH₂) and bis[3,3'-di(*m*-hydroxyphenylazo)]-2,2'-dihydroxydinaphthalene (L'H₄).

With a view to prepare inorganic polymers using multidentate Schiff bases and azodyes as ligands¹, the present work reports fourteen inorganic complex dimers containing NOON and ONOONO donor azodye ligands.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses indicate the dimeric stoichiometry, [M₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆], [M'₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂], [M₂L'(H₂O)₆] and [M'₂L'(H₂O)₂] of the complexes, where M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}; M' = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₂ = bis[3,3'-di(*p*-nitrophenylazo)]-2,2'-dihydroxydinaphthalene; L'H₄ = bis[3,3'-di(*m*-hydroxyphenylazo)]-2,2'-dihydroxydinaphthalene.

The complexes are stable upto 135°, indicating coordinated nature of the water molecules. All the complexes are amorphous. They are insoluble in common organic solvents but feebly soluble in dimethylformamide. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the low Λ_M

values (3.7–5.2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

IR spectra of ligand LH₂ reveal one broad band at 3150–3250 cm^{-1} and L'H₄ two sharp peaks at 3485 and 3402 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of O–H...N intramolecular hydrogen bonding. These bands are absent in the metal chelates, showing deprotonation of the phenolic OH groups². The bands appearing at 1645 and 1510 cm^{-1} (LH₂) and 1617 and 1511 cm^{-1} (L'H₄) in the azodyes can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibrations, respectively³. The appearance of these bands at *ca.* 1605, 1500 (LH₂) and *ca.* 1610, 1495 cm^{-1} (L'H₄) in the complexes suggests the bonding of the ligands to the metal ions through azo nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms, respectively. The presence of coordinated water molecules in all the complexes is ascertained by the broad band at 3350–3550 cm^{-1} followed by small sharp peaks at *ca.* 840 cm^{-1} assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations⁴, respectively. The evidence of bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at 421–450 (M–N) and 500–510 cm^{-1} and (M–O)⁵.

The subnormal magnetic moments of the Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes indicate M–M interaction in a dinuclear structure⁶. Both the Ni^{II} complexes are red in color and are diamagnetic in nature.

In the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes, the bands at ~8880, 17850, 20770 and 32320 cm^{-1} can be attributed transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, and CT band, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry around the cobalt ions⁷. The spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at around 16725, 17130 and 19310 cm^{-1} which are ascribed to ${}^6A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\sigma_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\sigma_1)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} {}^4E_g(\sigma_1)$ transitions, respectively, in support of an octahedral stereochemistry around Mn^{II} ions⁸. The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes show two bands at ~16570 and 19050 cm^{-1} , a diagnostic of a square-planar geometry. The assignments for these two bands are ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^2E_g$, respectively⁹. In the Ni^{II} complexes, two bands at ~16490 and 17285 cm^{-1} are assign-

able to ${}^1A_{1g}$, $\rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^1E_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, supporting a square-planar geometry. The diamagnetic nature of the complexes further support this configuration¹⁰.

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of the ligands LH_2 and $\text{L}'\text{H}_4$ show a complex pattern at δ 7.0–8.0 and 7.1–7.9 due to eighteen phenyl protons respectively.

The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ has been recorded at X-band. It shows of $g_{\perp} = 2.1222$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.2058$. The axial symmetry parameter (G) is found to be 1.68 which shows strong exchange interaction among Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell¹¹. The g_{\parallel} value is < 2.3 , indicating covalent nature of the complex^{12,13}. $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ was found to be ESR silent. This type of spectrum could be due to dynamic or pseudorotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or due to extensive exchange coupling operating between Cu-Cu ions¹⁴.

The X-ray diffraction study (powder method) of the compounds $[\text{Ni}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ have been indexed in X-ray diffractometer and unit cell parameters like

Table 1. X-Ray diffraction data of the complexes

Compd.	Unit cell parameters	Density g/cc	Possible geometry
$[\text{Ni}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$2\theta = 10.4, 12.2, 13.8, 16.3, 17.4, 20.4, 21.9, 25.6, 26.5, 28.7, 30.3, 31.5, 33.1, 34.6, 38.6, 41.4, 44.1, 44.9, 45.5, 46.8, 52.6, 54.8, 55.7$ $A = 8.708 \text{ \AA}$, $B = 15.629 \text{ \AA}$, $C = 7.264 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 93.390^\circ$, $\beta = 90.555^\circ$, $\gamma = 102.100^\circ$, volume = 964.66 \AA^3	0.69	Triclinic
$[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	$2\theta = 12.2, 12.9, 14.3, 16.0, 16.3, 16.7, 17.3, 18.7, 19.4, 23.0, 23.9, 25.5, 26.2, 28.3, 28.9, 29.4, 31.3, 32.0, 32.3, 35.4, 39.4, 44.1, 49.6$ $A = 11.255 \text{ \AA}$, $B = 22.390 \text{ \AA}$, $C = 9.527 \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = 94.798^\circ$, $\beta = 96.605^\circ$, $\gamma = 96.122^\circ$, volume = 2360.20 \AA^3	0.62	Triclinic

$A, B, C, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$ and volume of the unit cell and density have been calculated (Table 1). The calculated value of n is found to be 1/2 for the Ni^{II} complex and 1.0 for the Cu^{II} complex, which agree well with the suggested stereochemistry of the complexes. The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes appear to be four-coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based on analytical, IR and conductance data.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The ligands LH_2 and $\text{L}'\text{H}_4$ were prepared by the coupling reaction between the corresponding diazonium chlorides derived from *p*-nitroaniline and *m*-aminophenol with alkaline solution of di- β -naphthol at 0–5°, respectively.

The complexes: A mixture of ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides and the ligand solutions was heated at 60° for 0.5 h. After cooling, pH of the solution was raised by adding conc. ammonia slowly with constant stirring. The complexes precipitated were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum. All compounds gave satisfactory metal and N analyses.

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